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PURULENT-DESTRUCTIVE DISEASES OF THE SCROTUM AND TREATMENT METHODS

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Resume.

Epididymo-orchitis is an acute inflammation of the testicle and its appendage, requiring emergency surgical treatment. Ignoring the symptoms of the disease threatens purulent melting of the corresponding structures with complete loss of their function.

Keywords: *Epididymo-orchitis, photodynamic therapy, acute urinary tract infection, prostate enlargement, treatment.*

Introduction.

Epididymo-orchitis is a urological disease that threatens the development of serious complications. If the immune defense is reduced or medical care is delayed, the pathology progresses to purulent epididymo-orchitis. Against this background, additional damage to other organs of the genitourinary system occurs.

The most unfavorable outcome is urological sepsis with purulent melting of the testicle. Multiple organ failure may develop, threatening the patient's life. The danger of epididymo-orchitis progression also lies in the development of a bilateral process. Therefore,

the patient requires emergency hospitalization to prevent the development of the described complications.

The clinical picture of the pathology depends on the severity and nature of the penile injury. Typical signs:

- severe pain syndrome;
- hemorrhages and hematomas in the area of damage;
- increase in penis volume;
- blood in the urine;
- inability to urinate.

The severity of clinical symptoms depends on the characteristics of the specific case.

Emergency diagnostics for acute epididymoorchitis is aimed at quickly assessing the condition of the testicle and its appendage with the selection of optimal treatment tactics. For this purpose, a visual examination is performed, as well as an ultrasound examination (US) of the scrotum organs.

A diagnosis can be clarified using a set of laboratory tests. The doctors at SM-Clinic pay special attention to the general and biochemical blood test (inflammation markers), coagulogram, analysis for the infectious group (HIV, syphilis, hepatitis B, C) and others.

To eliminate pain and stabilize the patient's condition, urologists urgently perform a novocaine blockade of the spermatic cord according to Lorin-Epstein. In the case of a mild form of epididymoorchitis, conservative treatment with antibiotics and anti-inflammatory drugs is subsequently allowed.

In moderate and severe forms of the disease, a revision of the scrotum organs is performed under general anesthesia. It involves cutting the protein membrane of the scrotum in order to improve blood flow (detorzio) of the affected testicle. The operation helps to preserve the viability of the organ, eliminate clinical symptoms and improve the general well-being of the patient with epididymoorchitis.

Photodynamic therapy is based on the dynamic interaction of three components: a photosensitizer, light energy and molecular oxygen. Their interaction damages the target tissue and simultaneously activates immune-modulating processes. Accordingly, the minimally invasive treatment method is used in a variety of ways - from oncological diseases to off-label indications such as skin rejuvenation.

Photodynamic therapy (PDT) was first described in 1890, when medical student Oscar Raab discovered that microorganisms incubated with acridine red dyes died after exposure to light [1]. With the support of his professor Hermann von Tappeiner, this discovery led to the first clinical application of PDT in 1903. Later, von Tappeiner published a textbook together with Albert Jodlbauer in which this phenomenon was characterized as an oxygen-dependent process and a "photodynamic reaction" [2, 3].

Since its first description, PDT has developed enormously as a minimally invasive form of therapy. It found its way into dermatology with the development of topical photosensitizers (PS) in the 1990s. Today, PDT is established as an effective treatment option for oncological diseases and is increasingly also used for non-oncological indications such as photoaging, viral warts, acne and leishmaniasis.

PDT is based on the uptake of a PS which, when stimulated by light of a specific wavelength, reacts with oxygen and triggers a series of photochemical reactions in the target tissue, resulting in the formation of reactive oxygen species (ROS). These cytotoxic photoproducts initiate a cascade of biochemical processes that lead from damage to death of the target tissue [4]. Two types of reactions can occur, generating superoxide anion radicals and reactive singlet oxygen molecules. These destroy tumor cells through direct cell death (necrosis or apoptosis), vascular damage with tissue ischemia, immune modulation or through a combination of these factors [5].

The extent of cytotoxicity and tissue damage caused by PDT is multifactorial and depends on the type of PS, its extracellular and intracellular accumulation, the total dose administered, the irradiation intensity, the status of tissue oxygenation and the time interval between PS administration and light exposure [5].

Given the ease of application of topical PS and irradiation of the skin, it is not surprising that PDT is increasingly used as both lesion- and field-directed therapy [6]. Compared to other therapeutic procedures, topical PDT offers the possibility of treating multiple lesions simultaneously. The low invasiveness, good efficacy and tolerability, and excellent cosmetic results make PDT a valuable therapeutic option that can be used alone or as an adjunct to other standard therapies [7, 8].

- In general, PDT is a very efficient, well-tolerated treatment method with excellent cosmetic results that can be used for a wide range of tumorous, inflammatory and infectious diseases.
- It is expected that the treatment protocol will be further optimized in the future and new indications for topical PDT will be found.

Conclusions: Chronic orchiepididymitis is a disease that can lead to dangerous complications, in particular, to infertility. Against the background of the inflammatory process, sperm maturation (spermatogenesis) is disrupted, which leads to a deterioration in the quality of the spermogram. In severe cases, a man loses the ability to conceive a child naturally, and the couple is often forced to resort to assisted reproductive technologies. To avoid such a problem, it is very important for every man to seek help from a doctor and begin treatment when the first symptoms of epididymoorchitis appear. Correctly selected therapy will help stop the inflammatory process and, with a high degree of probability, reduce the risk of complications to zero.

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